

Supplementary Table 1. Validated parameters and acceptance criteria.

Parameter	Procedure	Acceptance criteria
Linearity	5 calibration curves in 5 different days	$r^2 \geq 0.99$ Calibrators residuals $\pm 20\%$
LOD	Analysis of blank nail/hair samples at decreasing concentrations in 2 different days (n=6)	Two MRM transitions with a signal to noise ratio >3 and adequate ion ratio
LOQ	Analysis of blank samples at the lowest calibrator concentration in 2 different days (n=6)	Two MRM transitions with a signal to noise ratio >10 , 80%-120% of nominal concentration and $\%CV < 20\%$
Selectivity	Endogenous interferences: 10 blank samples from different sources spiked with IStd Exogenous interferences: Blank samples fortified with 36 common drugs of abuse and medicines at 25 ng/mg.	No interferences detected
Carryover	Analysis of a blank matrix sample immediately after the highest calibrator (n=3)	Calculated concentration $< LOD$
Accuracy	Analysis of 3 replicates at low, medium and high QC concentrations in 5 different days (n=15)	80%-120% of the nominal concentration
Intra-assay, inter-assay and total imprecision	Analysis of 3 replicates at low, medium and high QC concentrations in 5 different days (n=15)	$\%CV < 20\%$
Matrix effect	At low and high QC concentrations, comparing mean peak areas in blank samples (n=10) fortified after extraction with mean peak areas of the analytes fortified in the mobile phase (n=10)	-
Extraction efficiency	At low and high QC concentrations, comparing mean peak areas in blank samples fortified before extraction (n=10) with blank samples fortified after extraction (n=10)	-
Process efficiency	At low and high QC concentrations, comparing mean peak areas in blank samples fortified before extraction (n=10) with mean peak areas of the analytes fortified in the mobile phase (n=10)	-
Autosampler stability	At low, medium and high QC concentrations (n=3 each), comparing freshly prepared QC samples and after 72 hours in the autosampler at 6°C	Re-injected samples quantified within $\pm 20\%$ of freshly prepared samples

Supplementary Table 2. Imprecision (n=15) and accuracy (n=15) in nail and hair samples at low (30, 120 or 300pg/mg), medium (1500pg/mg) and high (15000pg/mg) QC concentrations.

Analyte	Intra-assay imprecision (%CV)			Inter-assay imprecision (%CV)			Total imprecision (%CV)			Accuracy (%CV)			
	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	
Nails	diOHTHC	6.4	2.5	-	0.9	1.4	-	6.4	2.9	-	102.9	99.5	-
	OHTHC	3.7	2.7	2.3	2.8	3.1	4.7	4.6	4.1	5.3	104.7	103.9	102.1
	THCCOOH	2.7	3.1	3.1	3.5	3.0	4.4	4.4	4.3	5.4	100.4	103.2	101.4
	CBD	6.0	3.5	1.9	1.3	2.9	0.8	6.1	4.5	2.0	102.4	104.5	105.4
	CBN	0.0	4.2	1.5	0.0	2.5	2.8	0.0	4.9	3.1	100.0	107.4	109.1
	THC	0.0	2.2	3.0	0.0	3.3	1.7	0.0	4.0	3.4	100.0	108.7	107.4
Hair	diOHTHC	3.8	1.8	--	3.9	2.6	--	4.8	3.2	--	106.0	109.8	--
	OHTHC	3.5	2.0	3.2	3.1	1.1	2.6	4.7	2.3	4.1	105.1	108.4	104.1
	THCCOOH	4.8	2.3	3.0	1.6	3.5	2.0	5.1	4.2	3.6	102.6	106.3	101.0
	CBD	4.5	5.0	5.4	1.8	3.0	1.3	4.8	5.8	5.5	101.5	102.7	103.2
	CBN	2.4	1.6	4.1	2.7	3.6	5.6	3.6	3.9	6.9	107.7	101.3	101.0
	THC	3.1	1.6	3.6	2.0	3.3	4.7	3.7	3.7	5.9	107.2	103.6	102.4

diOHTHC: 8- β -11-dihydroxy- Δ 9-tetrahydrocannabinol; OHTHC: 11-hydroxy- Δ 9-tetrahydrocannabinol; THCCOOH: 11-nor-9-carboxy- Δ 9-tetrahydrocannabinol; CBD: cannabidiol; CBN: cannabinol; THC: Δ 9-tetrahydrocannabinol

Supplementary Table 3. Cannabinoid concentrations in cosmetically/medically treated samples.

Sample	Matrix	CBD (pg/mg)	CBN (pg/mg)	THC (pg/mg)	Cosmetic/Medical treatment
1	Fingernails	NEG	NEG	NEG	Nail polish/remover
	Toenails	NEG	NEG	31.3	None
3	Fingernails	12945.5	1066.2	11905.6	None
	Toenails	NEG	20.3	52.7	Antifungal treatment
12	Fingernails	3713.7	1108.7	6852.7	Nail polish/remover
	Toenails	NEG	NEG	NEG	None
14	Fingernails	NEG	26.1	60.3	None
	Toenails	NEG	NEG	38.3	Nail polish/remover
23	Fingernails	885.7	390.2	7498.8	Nail polish/remover
	Toenails	NEG	36.8	545.4	None